

An Introduction to the Theory of Open Government

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Abstract

Today, many governments from all around the world have taken serious steps to create positive social and economic changes and to reduce corruption in society. Open Government offers solutions to solve the problems and challenges of society, including administrative corruption, little communication between the government and the people, and weak cooperation between the components of the government and the administrative system. Open Government is a growing movement that encourages governments to make their information and data available to the public as much as possible, so that access to them is free, to increase government transparency and accountability and lead to increased citizen participation and economic growth. Therefore, the new concept of the government has been re-formed, emphasizing the interaction between the people and the government. The purpose of this research is to deal with the theoretical foundations and concepts related to Open Government.

Keywords: Open Government, Transparency, Participation, Cooperation;

1. Introduction

The lack of timely and effective government intervention and the speed of changes have sometimes caused severe regional and global crises. The old mechanisms of regulation, regulations and processes related to the approval and implementation of policies and their monitoring, when they are faced with rapid changes and developments, have little ability, and mechanisms must be New, intelligent and effective at the national and regional level, while maintaining the principles of the democratic process, they can change quickly. Based on this, the concept of open government has gained a special place in the last decade. In open government, citizens are viewed as collaborators, and a network structure prevails in such a way that the elements of the network do not have top-to-bottom relationships and members are in communication and at the same level. The role of government institutions is more as a communication facilitator. Also, in open government, information technology plays a fundamental and very important role and provides the platform needed for dialogue between network elements, common decision-making and cooperation among network members. The open government is based on three elements of transparency, participation and cooperation. Open government is a new phenomenon related to the concept of electronic government, which emphasizes the status of information. And it is built around a shared relationship between governments and citizens, where both are involved in solving problems. The phenomenon of open government is closely related to electronic government based on the extensive use of information and communication technologies (ICT). Public administration researchers have stated that the focus has shifted to open technology and open data in the past two decades. And there is a close connection between open government and e-government. Open government is not a sub-dimension of electronic government, nor is it a different concept, but it is electronic government with a greater focus on the state of information [1].

The "Open Government Participation" movement was formed in order to fight corruption, increase public participation and use new technologies to create more open, effective and responsive governments. Open government can be considered as a new interactive value chain and cooperation between public administration and citizens through the systematic integration of external players in the governance process. By implementing open government, the government becomes wider, actively seeks cooperation and partnerships with its citizens, shares its resources, and strives to improve transparency as much as possible, thus it can be called participatory government [2]. The open government movement is a global phenomenon. Governments and local authorities in countries such as the United States, Australia, New Zealand, the Netherlands, Sweden, Spain, Denmark and Austria make their data available to the public by publishing data on the web. The main reasons for implementing open government are to increase democratic accountability, increase transparency, provide public services designed by citizens and stimulate economic growth [3]. With the implementation of open government in the country, the bureaucratic structures become a flexible and open structure. Currently, considering the conditions of the country, we seriously need to adopt a suitable approach in the field of open government.

2. Theoretical foundations and background

In 2008, the newly elected Obama administration faced both new normative dilemmas and criticisms of previous governance models. Normative dilemmas related to the government's covert behavior after the 9/11 terrorist attack and the war in Afghanistan, which created a great deal of normative pressure for government transparency [4]. The Open Government Directive, which was promulgated on December 8, 2009 in the United States, foregrounded the principles of transparency, participation and cooperation as the cornerstones of an open government. The directive directed federal agencies to implement these principles by expanding access to government information (including reducing the backlog of Freedom of Information requests), improving the quality of government information, and creating and institutionalizing a focused "culture of open government." Emerging technologies, which have the potential to expand new forms of communication between government and people, are considered. The directive also instructed relevant agencies to propose revisions to any existing policies that may create barriers to the use of new technologies to advance open government goals. Organizations that followed this guideline subsequently used the Internet and the Web as well as the new capabilities provided by social media in open government programs [5].

2.1. Open Government

Defining the concept of open government is not simple, because it has many aspects and factors. One of the most reliable definitions is provided by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, which states that "open government is the transparency of government actions, access to government services and information, and the government's responsiveness to new ideas, demands and needs". Open government provides a level of citizen access to government information to participate in government decision-making. [6] At the macro level, open government is usually conceptualized by considering three principles: transparency, participation, and cooperation [7].

A model of open government is presented in figure (1).

Figure 1. Open government model [8].

- Transparency

Transparency in government means that government information and management decisions should be accessible and understandable to all citizens. [9] Transparency is the first initiative proposed by the Obama administration, where a website (www.data.gov) was created for access to federal data. The open government's transparency dimension revolves around data and information. [10].

- Participation

Participation is the participation of citizens in the decision-making process. The purpose of participation is to promote social and political responsibility. [10] Organizations should try to make public participation easier through devices and applications such as mobile phones. Efforts should be made for the public to access government data and participate and collaborate using smart phones, tablets, laptops and other devices [11].

The following factors can increase citizen participation:

1. Motivation of citizens
2. Democratic culture
3. Citizens' sense of responsibility
4. Extensive use of social media
5. Availability of feedback mechanisms
6. Variety of citizens' skills and capabilities
7. Sufficient budget resources to create open government data
8. The availability of a legal and political framework that mandates the publication of government information [12].

- Cooperation

Some organizations use partnership and cooperation interchangeably and do not distinguish between them in their open government programs. However, it is necessary to distinguish between the two. Participation refers to public participation in relatively simple interactive communications such as blogging, microblogging, social networking, photo/video sharing, and brainstorming. It basically relies on social media to connect people and help them share their ideas. On the other hand, collaboration refers to public participation in complex tasks or projects that aim to produce specific outputs. Such tasks include writing, group editing of documents, developing wiki applications, developing open source software, organizing events, etc. Collaboration relies on shared social media such as Wikis, Google Docs, and social business software. Open collaboration should go beyond inter-organizational collaboration and include not only the public sector but also the private sector. Organizations implement and embed open collaboration mechanisms in their open government tools and processes so that anyone can participate in the collaboration process anywhere, anytime. Open collaboration creates synergistic effects and leads to saving time, cost, higher quality and more innovation for government services and policymaking [11]. Unlike the partnership view that values collective expertise, the collaborative strategy emphasizes understanding innovative solutions rather than expanding partnerships. Most importantly, the collaboration strategy focuses on engaging non-profit organizations, the private sector and companies equipped with the necessary capacities to develop new strategies or services through continuous collaboration with the government [7].

- Open Data

Open data are data that can be accessed and used by all stakeholders and can be freely distributed [10]. Open data has features such as availability, comprehensibility, completeness, timeliness, error-free and security [13]. Publishing data stimulates innovation and promotes economic growth. One of the important applications is that investors and companies can use open data for investment. Policy makers should also be ready to share their data. By publishing the data, users can verify the accuracy and validity of the results obtained from the data and can analyze the previously collected data. Data sharing is often seen as transparency and altruistic knowledge and progress. Open data can strengthen accountability, build trust and improve citizen satisfaction. Access to information about what governments are doing is increasingly recognized as an important precondition for democratic accountability and deliberation. One of the main advantages of opening a system is the ability to exploit the collective intelligence of people [14].

2.2. Moving from closed systems to open systems

The general public is outside the organizational boundaries and outside the hierarchical structure. In fact, the public is part of the data processing system. And they may process the data, combine it with other sources, and may even collect their own data (for example, through the use of their mobile phones). This is a shift in the traditional boundaries between public organizations and the public, where almost anyone in the world has access to data. The

boundaries of the traditional system are disappearing and the systems are opening. System theory draws attention to the important distinction between systems that interact with their environment and systems that are closed. Closed systems are much easier to manage because they are not affected by external factors that are often unpredictable in nature. Central planning and control can be used, because there is less possibility of interference from the environment. On the contrary, the flow in open systems cannot be defined in advance, but only directed. Opening up a system is often about bringing new perspectives into the system that can have a positive impact on solving problems, and opening up data to be used in ways not previously considered or anticipated. It is not seen. The opening of systems provides the opportunity to create feedback loops in which the government can learn from the people. The social context will also affect the closed system. The relationship between the government and its environment is subject to change, and the government must accept that traditional planning and control tools are no longer appropriate. New governance mechanisms, capabilities and processes are necessary to deal with these feedback loops [14].

2.3. Open Government Maturity Model

Lee and Kwak (2012) proposed an open government maturity model (OGIM) that government agencies can use as a reference model to assess their current level of open government. This model guides government organizations on their way to open government. They argue that there is a need for a logical sequence when promoting open government, and by following this sequence, organizations can minimize risk and effectively use the power of social media to engage with the public. They developed their model based on findings and insights from their qualitative analysis of field interviews with several federal executives and employees, relevant scholarly and professional sources, relevant websites and online information, and government documents and reports. The Open Government Maturity Model can be used by government agencies without major changes. The Open Government Maturity Model guides government agencies to implement their open government initiatives in a logical, orderly and systematic manner, while minimizing risks and maximizing organizational benefits. Lee and Kwak's model is shown in figure (2).

Figure 2. Open Government Maturity Model (OGIM)

One of the important principles of Lee and Kwak's open government maturity model is that a government organization should follow the order of the implementation steps instead of implementing all the steps at once or following a random sequence. Lee and Kwak (2012) argue that increasing data transparency is a necessary precondition for the implementation of the next steps. Organizations can increase open collaboration and realize inclusive engagement more effectively if they have already improved open collaboration. Simultaneous implementation of several phases is likely to create challenging issues of resources, budget, time, technology, cultural change, and public acceptance. By focusing on one implementation step at a time, organizations can effectively build infrastructure and capabilities for open government without overwhelming civil servants or the public. As shown in Figure 2, with the progress of the implementation stage, the general public will increasingly participate in government work, so there will be more value and benefits for both the government and it also creates for people. However, as the implementation phase increases, the technical and managerial complexity of open government initiatives also increases. As a result, organizations should expect to face more challenges and risks in the next stages of implementation [11].

Level 1- Initial conditions

Level one refers to the initial stage where there is little open government capability and social media is rarely used. Government agencies at level one mainly focus on disseminating information to the public. They lack interactive communication capabilities such as social media and web tools and rely on one-way and static communication methods. An organization has a website that provides general information about the organization to the public. However, the general public does not mainly participate in the management process of the organization. Organizations do not publish a lot of data and only limited data is available to the public. Organizations use few or no quantitative indicators to evaluate their website performance or public engagement.

Level 2 - Data transparency

Increasing data transparency should be the first step towards open government. However, the use of social media to promote open government is limited at this stage, as web applications can often provide sufficient capabilities to enhance data transparency. Since the amount of data in the information economy is increasing, level two organizations are focusing on increasing the transparency of government processes and performance by publishing relevant data online and sharing them with the public. Two important tasks at this stage are: (1) identifying valuable and high-impact data for the public and (2) improving and ensuring data quality in terms of accuracy, consistency, and timeliness.

Organizations in the second level should not publish all their data, which is not only impractical, but also inefficient. According to the Pareto Principle (i.e. the 20/80 rule) approximately 80% of effects are caused by 20% of causes. Therefore, organizations should focus on the 20% of their data that is most beneficial to the public. To do this, organizations must establish an effective governance structure and process to formally identify relevant data, ensure its quality, and release it in a timely manner. Data quality is very important because low quality data may contain false and misleading public information about government work and performance. When bad data is published and shared, this information damages the credibility of organizations and public trust in organizations. Therefore, organizations must make sure that only valid and accurate data is made available to the public. Data can also help increase public awareness of government work and provide insight into how to improve government performance. Therefore, increasing data transparency provides the basis for people's participation and cooperation in government work in order to mobilize public action, create value-added services and facilitate innovation. Finally, people should be able to use government data to make better decisions and improve their quality of life. In order to strengthen the public's effective use of government data, the data should be easily accessible and usable. Organizations should review people's feedback on the usefulness and accessibility of data for continuous improvement. However, at level two, the use of social media is very limited and most of the online communications are done through conventional methods such as websites or emails [11].

Level 3- Open Partnership

The third level of the open government maturity model focuses on improving people's open participation in government decision-making through various methods and tools. While at level two government data is provided to the public, at level three the government receives ideas and public knowledge. Organizations at level three strive to expose people's stories, conversations, ideas, and opinions to the public. To do this, organizations are turning to social media and web tools, including web chats, blogs, microblogging, social networking, photo and video sharing, and ideation tools. Unlike traditional feedback methods such as surveys and questionnaires, social media allows people to engage in informal, conversational interactions with government. Organizations at level three try to get public ideas, knowledge, expertise, and experiences through voting, polling, contests, blogging, microblogging, brainstorming, etc. While there are many social media tools out there, organizations tend to start with tools that are widely available and used by the public, such as Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube. Some of the benefits of increased open participation include real-time, immediate, diverse feedback, continuous and community-based dialogue, reduced time and cost for innovation, and innovation expansion. Through informal and ongoing interactions with the public, level three organizations strive to foster open government culture and practices. It is important for organizations at this stage to have the ability to respond to public feedback in a timely and continuous manner. This capability requires formal processes, coordination mechanisms and dedicated staff who respond to public comments [11].

Level 4 - Open collaboration

Once government agencies have increased data transparency and open collaboration, the next step is to foster open collaboration between government agencies, the public, and the private sector. Therefore, organizations at level four collaborate with other organizations using government data and public opinions and feedbacks and create government value-added services for the public and private sectors. Open collaboration creates synergistic effects and leads to time savings, cost, higher quality and more innovation for government services and policymaking and legislation. The Open Government Maturity Model suggests that government organizations should go through various implementation stages

in an orderly manner. The Pareto principle or the 80/20 rule applies not only to level two but also to levels three and four. They should only choose high-value, high-impact initiatives and focus on enhancing what works instead of worrying too much about unnecessary issues [11].

Level 5- ubiquitous engagement

Organizations at level five, which builds on levels two through four, take transparency, participation, and collaboration to the next level of public engagement. Organizations improve and adjust existing open government initiatives to maximize their benefits. Additionally, they are expanding their portfolio of open government initiatives to further benefit the public. Organizations at level five strive to achieve two important goals. First, public engagement through mobile devices and applications becomes available everywhere. At level five, the public accesses and collaborates with government data using smartphones, tablets, laptops, and other devices. Second, various methods, tools and services of public engagement are seamlessly integrated within and between government agencies so that the public can easily engage in various activities without having to subscribe to different programs. Five-level organizations create an effective governance structure and process for continuous improvement and innovation of public engagement programs. In addition to these organizations, the government, private sector and other stakeholders form a sustainable ecosystem and a cycle for effective public engagement. They measure not only financial performance but also non-financial performance such as innovation and learning. Openness becomes a norm for government culture and people are constantly involved in government activities. As a result, the vision and promises of the open government guidelines are fully realized at level five [11].

2.4. Factors affecting the implementation of open government

Factors affecting the implementation of open government include the following:

1. **Culture:** Among the indicators of culture, it is possible to mention the preparation of employees to accept open government, identifying stakeholders, communication channels for interaction, encouraging participation and cooperation.
2. **Technology:** in order to implement the open government in the electronic platform, paying attention to the indicators of "design and analysis of systems", "considering security", "using practical services", "using suitable tools", "Considering system architecture (using the web)", "Identifying processes", "Technical support during updates and existing errors", "Considering backup" and "Infrastructure" , It is essential.
3. **Policy-making:** formulation of strategies and policies are important and influential factors in the implementation of open government. that "strategic planning", "attention to laws", "legal dimensions", "internal directives", "attention to privacy" are among the factors mentioned in the framework of the open government of the United States of America [15] [16].
4. **Legal protections:** such as issuing a license for public access to information, the law on personal data protection and privacy, the provisions of the freedom of the press law regarding the right to obtain government information and, more specifically, official documents.
5. **Public support and awareness:** Public awareness and support of open government projects leads to innovation and creation of new ideas and greater participation of citizens and empowerment of citizens. Public support leads government officials to improve policies, release more data sets, and collaborate with users [17].
6. **Data catalog:** In order to prepare the data catalog, a group of experts classify the information. And they categorize data and information into confidential classified information and unclassified information. The highest official of any organization or one of the responsible officials of the organization confirms the accuracy of the information. The publication of data should be done in a selective and selected manner and the quality of data should be published in such a way that they have the ability and value to be published. Because the publication of low-quality data leads to the confusion of stakeholders, abuse of individuals or other organizations [15].
7. **Human resources:** Human resources are valuable and unique assets for the success of an organization. It is necessary to hold workshops, discussions and meetings with the aim of increasing the skills of government officials and employees in order to increase their ability [18]. The existence of specialized manpower and a sufficient number of manpower is

one of the effective factors in carrying out projects and in order to make decisions and deal with issues related to information technology [15].

8. Financial: The implementation of open government requires financial support, especially when resources are limited [18]. Providing financial resources and budget allocation are among the key issues in the feasibility and implementation of open government. The budget allocation can include "the cost of purchasing supplies and equipment", "software", "manpower training", "operational costs" and "communication costs" [15].

2.5. Consequences of open government implementation

Table (1) shows some of the consequences of open government.

Table 1. Consequences of implementing open government

Row	Consequences	Reference
1	Transparency increase	[11], [14], [19]
2	Responsiveness increase	[11]
3	Trust increase Government	[14], [20]
4	Citizen satisfaction increase	[14], [20]
5	Improving services to citizens and providing new government services for citizens	[14], [19]
6	Increasing the participation of citizens in making decisions about their own civil affairs through discussion and consultation	[14]
7	Improvement of policy making processes	[14]
8	Use of collective wisdom	[14]
9	Creating new insights in the public sector	[14]
10	Economic growth and stimulation of competition and development of innovation	[14], [19]
11	Improving processes, products or services	[14]
12	New products and services development	[14], [19]
13	Availability of information for investors and companies	[14], [19]
14	Fair decision making with the possibility of comparison	[14]
15	Optimizing and simplifying administrative procedures	[3], [19]
16	Increasing employee motivation due to greater interaction with stakeholders, emphasizing the external importance of their work	[3]
17	Increasing the improvement of the public image of government departments	[3]
18	Increasing productivity and saving financial	[3]
19	Limiting fraud and preventing corruption and other forms of irresponsible behavior	[3]
20	Stabilizing and legitimizing policies	[3]
21	Fast and easy access to reliable data as a valuable resource for creating new business models	[3], [14]
22	Increasing efficiency and effectiveness	[10]
23	Increasing public awareness and knowledge	[11]
24	Cultural shift towards openness	[11]

Table 1 (continued).

Row	Consequences	Reference
25	Knowledge sharing between departments	[11]
26	Possibility to report errors by users	[3]
27	Automated data service to reduce human intervention	[3]
28	Improving public policies	[19]
29	Improving democratic decision-making	[20]
30	Possibility to receive feedback on service quality	[20]
31	Increasing the synergistic effect of inter-organizational cooperation: saving time, cost and output with higher quality	[11]
32	Avoiding rework in policy making	[3]
33	Making it possible to compare data	[3]
34	Increasing the responsibility of statesmen	[3], [11]
35	Informing the people about the reasons for not achieving the government's goals	[3]

3. Discussion and conclusion

The purpose of this research was to investigate concepts related to open government. Open government is a new phenomenon that has attracted a lot of attention in recent years. Open government will play an important role in the future to make management more open and responsive, reduce costs and increase efficiency, strengthen the economic system and balance social imbalances. The government promotes transparency and participation to enable effective monitoring. Full, immediate and widespread disclosure of public data leads to an accountable and transparent government. Addressing the concept of open government and implementing open government in the country can lead to the following:

1. Localization of open government principles in the country
 2. Improving the quality of decision-making and policy-making in the country
 3. Helping justice-oriented, transparency in the regulation of administrative laws and regulations
 4. Help to empower the government and executive system of the country in order to respond more efficiently
 5. Attention to effectiveness and efficiency in administrative processes and methods in order to provide better services.
- Finally, policy makers and statesmen are suggested to take the first step in order to provide the infrastructure needed for the implementation of open government in the country.

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